

DAMAGE DETECTION IN A COMPOSITE SKIN-STRINGER PANEL USING LAMB WAVE PROPAGATION TECHNIQUE: A NUMERICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Composite structure assemblies are usually prone to disbond, when submitted to fatigue or extreme loads. The integrity of composite skin-stringer joints is evaluated by the Lamb wave propagation technique using the finite element method. The structure of interest is composed of two carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) plates bonded together with an adhesive film as a skin-stringer assembly. Two different bonding conditions are investigated: undamaged and damaged (with disbond). The disbond is introduced by removing an adhesive layer representing a zero volume defect. The primary anti-symmetric mode (A0) is excited by imposing an out-of-plane displacement on the surfaces and A-scans (defined as displacement time history at a location) are performed across the bond line before and after the joint. In finite element modelling, a seven cycle harmonic wave with 350 kHz tone-burst is applied to the structure, using transient analysis. Symmetric and anti-symmetric Lamb wave modes are presented for undamaged and damaged joints in the time domain. It was found that the joint affects both modes, however the influence of the defect on the anti-symmetric mode is more visible. The level of reflection and transmission of the anti-symmetric Lamb wave mode is different for undamaged and damaged joints. From the scanning across-the-bond, the quality of the joint can be assessed by comparing baseline data and targeted area signals. The results verify that guided wave propagation is very effective for flaw detection in composite structural assemblies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been increasingly used in engineering structures during the last decades. Despite enhancements in terms of specific strength and stiffness, their susceptibility to delamination and disbond is still a main concern. Therefore, non-destructive inspection (NDI) methods have been used for detailed inspection of these structures and over the last 50 years, these techniques have attained maturity in various applications, playing a vital role in assessment of the integrity and durability of the structures [1]. Traditional NDI approaches are usually conducted at regular scheduled intervals during the lifetime and cannot provide descriptive information about structural integrity in a real-time manner. Moreover, almost all of the existing NDI methods require extremely time-consuming point-by-point inspection. Furthermore, it is also difficult to carry equipment to a site and detect damages in complex structures [2].

Structural health monitoring (SHM), as an improved and retrofitted version of traditional NDI, is proposed for continuous inspection of the structural features including composite joint to evaluate the integrity of the joint. SHM systems replace scheduled maintenance with as-needed (condition-based) maintenance, thus save the cost of unnecessary maintenance as well as improve the level of safety through considering of working condition updates [1]. SHM is a major area of interest for the

aerospace community, especially considering aging aircraft where the growing maintenance costs, estimated at \$10.4 billion worldwide annually, can reduce their economic life [3]. It has been demonstrated that an effective SHM technique can reduce the total maintenance cost compared to traditional NDE approaches by more than 30% for an aircraft fleet [4]. Among the different approaches of SHM, ultrasonic guided waves (Lamb wave) in solid media have become a critically important subject. New faster, more sensitive and more economical ways of looking at materials and structures have become possible when compared to the previously used normal beam ultrasonic or other inspection techniques. The wave propagation methods usually make use of piezoelectric transducers as to generate waves and measure the signature of the echoes that may be influenced by any inhomogeneity (stiffener or defect).

1.1 Propagation of guided waves

Guided waves (Lamb waves) were first described by Lamb [5], and were used for inspection of homogeneous isotropic materials. They are ultrasonic waves that are guided between two parallel free surfaces, such as the upper and lower surfaces of a plate. Interaction of Lamb waves with structural damage can significantly influence their propagation, accompanied by wave scattering effects such as reflection, transmission and mode conversion [1]. For delamination [6, 7], impact-induced delamination [8-10], matrix cracks [11], thermal and fatigue effects [12], it has been shown that each discontinuity affects the wave scattering parameters. The location of damage can be determined by measuring the arrival time of scattered waves and its size is evaluated by degree of attenuation. However, guided wave propagation in bonded structures [13] was not investigated in detail, despite the fact that these features are very common in aircraft structures. The comparison between guided wave approach and other conventional approaches shows that the current commercial use of SHM system based on guided wave propagation still requires additional research to be optimized for damage detection of disbonds in bonded composite structures [14].

Previous studies show that two strategies can be employed for inspection of bonded joints [13]. The first approach examined in the literature is the “within-the-bond” method which allows using bond lines as a waveguide resulting in minimization of the influence of complex geometrical features on wave behavior [15]. It has been shown that using this approach, a primary anti-symmetric mode (A0) below 200 kHz frequency range is a good candidate for effective inspection of composite-to-metallic bonded structures [16]. The “Across-the-bond” method is the second strategy, which has been employed in previous studies for damage detection in simple and complex metallic assemblies [18]. With this method, the degree-of-disbond in adhesive joints can be estimated by measuring the attenuation level of the A0 mode [19]. Guided wave tomographic imaging method based on frequency and wave mode tuning has good potential for SHM application of adhesive joints in composite skin-stringer structures [20].

In this paper, a two-dimensional transient finite element analysis is developed for the composite skin-stringer assembly. Ultrasonic guided waves (anti-symmetric excitation) are generated by displacement excitation at the top and bottom surface of the skin and A-scan measurement is used to examine the bonding condition. The objective is to evaluate the effect of the stringer as well as the disbond on the reflection and transmission behaviour of the wave forms in time domain.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Finite Element Modeling

In order to determine Lamb wave behaviour through the composite skin-stringer assembly, numerical simulations are carried out using the commercial finite element (FE) software, ANSYS. Geometry and detailed description of the joint and disbond are shown in Fig. 1. A two dimensional problem is defined using plane-strain assumption [21] representative of an infinite medium along the z-direction. CYCOM 5320-1 woven CFRP and adhesive film with material properties described in

Table 1 are used for modelling the composite joint.

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)	ρ (kg/m ³)
CFRP	82	82	0.34	5.2	1310
Adhesive	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.38	1420

Table 1: Material properties of woven CFRP and adhesive film used in FEM

Since each lamina represents plane weave material, 8 layers of plies are used for making a quasi-isotropic layup $[0/90/45/-45]_{2s}$ where the 0 degree direction is the x-direction. In the FE model, no damping was incorporated [21-23]. The thickness of each lamina is 0.212 mm. Since each individual part made of 8 plies, the thickness of the stringers and the skin is 1.7 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of composite skin-stringer geometry and location of transducers

To simulate the disbond; a portion of the adhesive is removed for the case of total disbond. No contact element is used for modelling the disbond [21-23]; therefore the disbond length has been modelled by de-merging the nodes, which is the same as a zero volume disbond [17, 21-22]. Square 2-D plane strain quadratic elements, which have a length of 0.25 mm, are used to make sure enough elements (at least 15 elements) are placed per wavelength. The PLANE183 element with eight nodes (four corners, four mid-side nodes) allows for the prediction of 2-D vibrations with two translational degrees-of-freedom at each node. Local mesh refinement is implemented around the stringer and disbond edges (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: The skin-stringer assembly in 2-D FEM (a), mesh refinement around the stringer (b)

2.2 EXCITATION OF LAMB WAVES

A seven cycle harmonic wave with 350 kHz tone-burst is applied using transient analysis. This excitation pulse corresponds to a 20 μs excitation duration. The total imaging time of 200 μs and time step size of 200 ns are chosen based on several convergence studies. The A0 mode is excited by applying an out-of-plane displacement in the same direction (out-of-phase excitation) at the top and bottom of the plate at $x=0$. The time and frequency representation of the input signal are depicted in Fig. 3. However, point-nodes are employed to introduce the excitation and capture the signal response in the form of displacement, the transmitter and receiver terms are used in the present study. The locations of the transmitter and the receivers (R1 and R2) on the structure are also depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 3: Y-displacement signal excitation applied at $x=0$; time (top) and frequency (bottom) domain representation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to characterize the wave propagation in the composite skin-stringer joint, the first simulation is performed on a simple composite plate (without stiffener) with the same material, geometry and sensor configuration described in Section 2 to identify the time-of-flight (TOF) of different wave packets. TOF of the peak of each envelope of a wave group was used as the representative time for computation of the group velocity of that wave mode. Arrival time of the incident A0 wave peak to the first receiver (R1) in the simple plate is 32.6 μs , as illustrated in Fig. 4. Therefore, the TOF of the incident wave from excitation point to the R1 location is calculated to be 23.2 μs (32.6-9.4). Similarly, the corresponding TOF of the reflected A0 mode from the right-end boundary is 182.6 μs . The group velocity (V_g) of a wave group is given by:

$$V_g = \Delta x / \Delta t \quad (1)$$

where Δx is the separation distance between two reception points and Δt is the difference in TOF of that wave group at these two points. The average group velocity of the A0 modes in the plate is 2694 m s^{-1} . Needless to say, since there is no stringer introduced in the laminate yet, the only two waveforms attributed to the incident and the right-end reflections are captured by R1. It is also noted that no symmetric wave packet is collected by R1.

Afterwards, the undamaged skin-stringer joint as described in Section 2.1 is studied. Both A0 and S0 modes captured by receivers R1 and R2 are presented in Fig. 5(a) and 5(b) respectively. From the

time of flight (TOF) calculation mentioned above, in Fig. 5(a), the first waveform corresponds to the incident wave propagating from $x=0$ towards the right; the second wave packet corresponds to the left-end reflection of the stringer captured by R1 at 66.3 μs . It is also noted that the wave interaction with the right-end of the stringer cause another relatively large waveform reflection captured at the time of 111 μs . Moreover, the next two waveforms captured between 130 μs to 175 μs are multiple reflections at the stringer ends [24].

Figure 4: A-scan of a simple composite plate at $x=62.5$ mm, out-of-phase excitation (A0 mode). A0 mode: dashed blue lines and S0 mode: solid red lines.

On the transmission side, the A0 and S0 mode captured by the receiver 2 are shown in Fig. 5(b). The incident and boundary reflection arrive at 92.4 μs and 133 μs . The stringer right-end transmitted wave packet gets to R2 just after the boundary reflected and they are partially combined, while the left-end wave form gets to R2 later at 175 μs . By comparing A0 and S0 modes, it is seen that at $x=62.5$ mm, the S0 mode amplitude is almost negligible at R1 location, of the order of 0.1% of the A0 amplitude. Whereas, the stronger S0 mode is captured by R2 with 15% of the A0 amplitude. This implies the S mode generation due to interaction of the incident A0 mode at the stringer edge. The new generated S0 mode on the transmitted side appeared earlier than the incident A0 mode, since the S0 mode traveled faster than the A0 mode [23].

(a)

Figure 5: A-scan of undamaged bonded skin-stringer at $x=62.5$ mm (a) and $x=237.5$ mm (b); A0 mode: dashed blue lines and S0 mode: solid red lines.

A detailed view of a section of the structure ($x=0$ mm to $x=115$ mm) is examined between the time period of $10 \mu\text{s}$ to $70 \mu\text{s}$, and is depicted in Fig. 6. It is noted that when the excitation wave packet is travelling at a group velocity of 2694 m/s to the right, it reaches the left-end of the stiffener at $42 \mu\text{s}$. Once the incident wave encounters the left-end of the stringer, it gets reflected back towards the left and this waveform is recorded by R1 at a time of $66.3 \mu\text{s}$.

Figure 6: Snapshots of Y-displacement of A0 mode propagating towards the left-end of the stringer; interaction and reflection at times (a) $10 \mu\text{s}$, (b) $20 \mu\text{s}$, (c) $30 \mu\text{s}$, (d) $40 \mu\text{s}$, (e) $50 \mu\text{s}$, (f) $60 \mu\text{s}$ and (g) $70 \mu\text{s}$.

Figure 7: A0 mode signal at 350 kHz captured by R1 for the composite skin-stringer assembly (a) the present study for 8-ply quasi-isotropic laminates as sub-assemblies, (b), 8-ply cross-ply laminates as sub-assemblies by tomographic imaging experiment [20]; for the baseline joint (undamaged): solid blue line, and the joint with defect: dashed black lines.

After the understanding of stringer effect on the guided wave behaviour in the joint region, the wave propagation mechanisms that take place through a damaged zone can be investigated. The first receiver in pulse-echo configuration captured the reflection waveforms from the disbond. A representative recorded signal between 100 μs and 130 μs for both the damaged and undamaged cases is plotted in Fig. 7(a). The results are compared to the guided wave tomographic imaging used in Ref. [20]. However, the lay-up of the skin and stringer in Ref. [20] is a cross ply (8-ply), the two results are in good agreement. The difference between the undamaged (baseline) and damaged signal reveals a combination of both amplitude change as well as phase shift of the waveforms. The phase change or a small delay is related to a local change of longitudinal and transverse bulk velocities [17]. Therefore, a pulse-echo configuration using A0 mode of guided waves can ensure an effective structural health monitoring for composite skin-stringer assembly.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The finite element modelling of guided wave propagation for two bonded composite plates as a skin-stringer assembly is developed in this paper. The adhesively bonded joint is modelled and damaged is introduced by removing adhesive film layer in a total disbond condition. The A0 mode Lamb wave is excited by harmonic excitation (with a frequency of 350 kHz) using out-of-plane displacement in a transient analysis. A-scan measurements were performed before and after the stringer and results were presented in the time domain. Using group velocity of the wave packets, the reflected and transmitted wave packets from the stringer are distinguished. The results also confirm that the quality of the joint can be assessed by comparing baseline and damaged A0 mode captured before the joint. Therefore, numerical simulation results justify the application of guided wave methods for disbond detection in a composite joint.

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